

TREATMENT OF SCAPHOID NONUNION WITH VASCULARIZED BONE GRAFT IN ADULTS

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Abstract

Despite advances in surgery and the understanding of bone healing, bone nonunion remains a challenge. Due to the retrograde blood supply of the proximal scaphoid fractures, the nonunion is much higher in these fractures. Nonunion of scaphoid is much common and there are many methods to treat this nonunion. Both vascularize and non-vascularized bone grafts were used with or without headless screw fixation, k-wires fixation or plate fixation, but results are controversial. But there is no gold standard treatment. In this study, we are using a vascularized bone graft and Kwire fixation to treat this non-union.

Objective:

To evaluate the outcome of vascularized bone graft in nonunion of the scaphoid.

Method

A total of 15 patients of both genders between 18 years to 50 years of age at the Mayo hospital from 1-4-19 to 30-5-20. All patients were admitted as outpatients after a complete investigation from an anesthesia point of view.

Results

The total number of patients was 10, with 7 male and 3 female, and the Mean age was 31.9 ± 5.8 years, ranging from 18 to 50 years. The mean age of the men and women was 28.6 ± 8.7 and 27.3 ± 7.5 years, respectively, with no significant differences. Union was achieved in all patients, mild sudek atrophy noted in 2 patients; the range of movements at the finger and wrist were acceptable range, infection noted. No implant failure was noted. no collapse or arthritis was noted after the last follow-up. Mean MWS was 61.28 in all the subjects, ranging from 49 to 90, six months after surgery. 1 (10%) were grouped as excellent, 7 (%) good, 2 (%) satisfactory, and 0 (%) poor.

Conclusion:

Vascularized bone graft is an easy, simple, and effective method to treat the nonunion of the scaphoid.

INTRODUCTION

5 to 25 percent of scaphoid fractures resulted in nonunion [1]. Higher rates of nonunion were noted in displaced fractures than nondisplaced fractures, showing the severity of injury [3]. Nonunion, malunion, or avascular necrosis were more common in both distal and proximal fractures of the scaphoid [4] These pole fractures are very unstable and difficult to handle. Due to retrograde blood supply of the proximal scaphoid fractures, the nonunion is much higher in these fractures. Non union of scaphoid is much common even a good pop treatment and there are many method to treat this non union both with vascularize and non vascularized bone grafts, with or without headless screw fixation, k-wires fixation or plate fixation. But there is no any gold standard treatment. 5 to 10 percent nonunion or malunion rate are still reported in the literature even with operation fixation and bone grafting [1], is the most common type of carpal bone fractures. The most common mechanism of scaphoid fracture are a fall on the outstretched hand or a motor vehicle accident or any sufficiently strong force on the hand. [2]. 60 to 70% of all carpal bone fractures consists of scaphoid fractures [1] and also second in in distal radial fractures [1] 80% approximately of the scaphoid bone surface is covered with cartilage and blood supply is retrograde manners so in fracture the blood supply to the proximal pole is interrupted leading to non union. [2] The delicate vasculature and initial force displacing the fractures are main complications causing a high rate of nonunion. [6] The rate of nonunion are as high as 10% even in the advancement of surgical technique and a humpback deformity was noted on the radiograph in case of avascular necrosis by fracture nonunion of proximal pole [7]. The carpal collapse and degenerative arthritis, are the final outcome not only causing personal and economic costs the quality of life is much disturbed. [8] The open reduction and internal fixation and bone grafting is ideal treatment. There are different types of bone graft, including nonvascularized and vascularized bone grafts and vascularized bone graft are much superior than non vascularized bone graft because they bring their blood supply

with them and also help to unite the non union [9],[10]

MATERIAL AND METHODS

A total 15 patients were studied of both gender between 18 years to 50 years of age at Mayo hospital from 1-4-19 to 30-5-20. All patients were admitted through out door after complete investigation for anesthesia point of view,

INCLUSION CRITERIA

1. Both gender
2. Adults between 18 to 50 year
3. established non union
4. Six month passed after initial trauma

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

1. patients with systemic musculoskeletal problems
2. bone tumors
3. bone infection
4. degenerative changes in wrist bones
5. radiologically proven scapholunate dissociation
6. bilateral involvement
7. with previous surgeries around wrist

The radiographic evaluation was made through the images in the following positions: neutral PA; PA with ulnar deviation of the wrist; profile; semi pronation oblique; and semi-supination oblique. The fracture was considered consolidated according to the presence of trabecular bone in at least three views without pain on the fracture site. [7]

We considered DISI when the scapholunate angle was larger than 60° or the radio-lunar angle was larger than 30°. [8]

NON-UNION

The union was considered to have occurred when there was no tenderness at the anatomical snuffbox and there was evidence of bony trabeculae crossing the fracture line or a sclerotic band present at the site of the fracture on at least three views. Mean time to radiological union for all fractures is nine weeks. [3],

OPERATION TECHNIQUE

In all patients a general anesthetic was given. A volar approach was used to expose the non union

and distal radius Radial artery identified and retracted laterally with flexor carpi radialis. Median nerve identified and retracted medially with long flexor of wrist and palmar longus, Pronator quadratus identified, pronation of forearm was done. Lateral and posterior radius bone identified. By using saw distal one third of pronator quadratus attached with bone was cut from the radius, about one third bone was attached with muscle. Muscle was detached up to the ulna. Now dissection is done at scaphoid. No signs of healing, cystic and fibrous changes and were noted at non union site. The nonunion site of the bone was debrided until punctuate bleeding was visualized in both proximal and distal part of bone. Both curette and burr were used and copious irrigation with saline was also done. Copious cancellus bone graft was taken from the distal radius and placed on between the non union site of scaphoid. Some cortical may also be placed if required to maintain the shape of the scaphoid. Then this nonunion site was fixed by two parallel

1mm two k-wires. The superior part of scaphoid bone is curettage and prepare a bed for vascularized graft. Then bone attached with pronator quadratus moved and attached on the scaphoid on already prepared bed and fixed by two 1mm k-wires, Stability checked and. Gentle wrist range of motion demonstrated excellent stability of the construct with no signs of impingement at the radiocarpal joint. Fluoroscopy confirmed appropriate reduction and hardware placement if available. Wound closed in layers. Pop cast applied in neutral position.

FOLLOW UP

The patient was discharged on next day, physiotherapy started next day. Stitches were removed after 14 days. Patients called on every month till union. All k-wires were removed after 2 months. The patient was placed into a Muenster cast for 4 weeks. At that time X-rays were performed out of cast.

Category	Score	Findings
Pain (25 points)	25	No pain
	20	Mild pain with vigorous activities
	20	Pain only with weather changes
	15	Moderate pain with vigorous activities
	10	Mild pain with activities of daily living
	5	Moderate pain with activities of daily living
	0	Pain at rest
Satisfaction (25 points)	25	Very satisfied
	20	Moderately satisfied
	10	No satisfied, but working
	0	No satisfied, unable to work
Range of motion (25 points)	25	100% percentage of normal
	15	75% - 99% percentage of normal
	10	50% - 74% percentage of normal
	5	25% - 49% percentage of normal
	0	0% - 24% percentage of normal
Grip strength (25 points)	25	100% percentage of normal
	15	75% - 99% percentage of normal
	10	50% - 74% percentage of normal
	5	25% - 49% percentage of normal
	0	0% - 24% percentage of normal
Final result (total points)	90 - 100	Excellent
	80 - 89	Good
	65 - 79	Fair
	<65	Poor

Mayo wrist Score (MWS) was used to assess the function out come

- 1.Pain
- 2.intensity
3. functional status
- 4., range of motion, and

5.grip strength.

Scores are recorded in four groups: 90-100: Excellent, 80-90: Good, 60-80: Satisfactory, below 60: poor.

Pain was categorized in four levels of "No pain", "Mild occasional", "Moderate tolerable", and "Severe to intolerable"

Physical activity was also categorized as "Returned to regular employment", "Restricted employment", and "Able to work but unemployed".

Range of motion in dorsiflexion, palmar flexion, radial flexion, and ulnar flexion in the affected

wrist was measured using a goniometer, and was reported as a percentage.

Grip strength was measured by asking the patient to squeeze the index finger of the examiner, and the strength was compared on the contralateral side using a dynamometer, and reported as a percentage.

Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (version 18, Chicago, IL, USA). Data are expressed as mean ± standard deviation for numerical variables and as percent (%) for categorical variables. Independent t-test, paired t-test, and Chi-square were used to analyze the data.

RESULT

Total patients were 10 with 7 were male 3 were female and Mean age was 31.9 ± 5,8 years ranging from 18 to 50 years. Mean age of the men and women was 28.6 ± 8.7 and 27.3 ± 7.5 years, respectively, with no significant differences.

Union was achieved in all patients, mild sudek atrophy noted in 2 patients 'range of movemrnts at finger

and wrist wre acceptable range .no any infection noted .no implaint failure was noted . no collapse oe arthritis was

noted after last follow up . . Mean MWS was 61.28 in all the subjects, ranging from 49 to 90 six months after surgery.

1 (10%) were grouped as excellent, 7 (30%) good, 2 (53.3%) satisfactory, and 0 (6.7%) poor

DISCUSSION

Scaphoid fractures is not usually assesd on initial X-rays in about 70% cases and computed tomography, bone scain, MRI, and ultrasound are neded.[2] MRI was considered the gold standard5 and computed tomography has gained more diagnostic importance now a days.[10] Yildirim et al.[11] proposed that ultrasound evaluation in the emergency room would increase the diagnostic power of this injury.

Fall with the flat hand in dorsiflexion and radial deviation of the wrist is most common mechanism of fractures.[12] Nonunion of scaphoid is managed by percutaneous screws fixation with or without bone graft,[10] fixation with Kirschner wires,[13] vascularized bone graft,9,14,15 and others that report using different types of screws. Despite advances in surgery and in the understanding of bone healing, bone nonunion remains a challenge.[16] Inadequate stability and inadequate reduction, a vascularity reduction and also the forces on the wrist bone are major causes of scaphoid non union.[18]

Four corners arthrodesis, resection proximal row carpectomy, radiocarpal arthrodesis are commonly used techniques in advanced nonunion and wrist arthritis [17] pure scaphoid excision or the pyrocarbon prosthesis considering the proper indication in each case[17].

Malizos et al.[19] and Liang et al.[20] showed 100% consolidation rate with vascularized bone graft based on different arterial supply.

Bullens et al., 23 treated scaphoid nonunion by a minimally invasive procedure using a percutaneous autologous corticocancellous bone graft. Average follow-up was done up to of 3.5

years. None of the patients had pain at work and a almost-normal range of motion was observed in all patients and grip strength was alsoat satisfactory level and progression to osteoarthritis was not noted.[23]

In one study, Herbert screw fixation, the Matti-Russe bone grafting, or the Kohlman modification of vascularized muscle pedicle graft procedure were done in patients, there was no significant difference between the union rate in the three technique, but in the Kohlman modification of vascularized muscle pedicle graft procedure there was less union time, and is recommended in old nonunion (>1 year) or proximal pole fractures.[24] The Matti-Russe technique, the Fisk-Fernandez technique, and vascularized bone grafting were used in one study and it was noted that there is no statistically significant difference in clinical and radiological outcomes; however, vascularized bone grafting got much short time for bone union.[25] Bertelli et al. worked on nonunion for more than 2 year nonunion. A vascularized bone graft harvested from the thumb and pedicled on the first dorsal metacarpal artery by a palmar approach. 90% patients got bone union with significant pain relief with improved range of motion and grip strength. [25] This union rate is also almost the same as in our study.

In two other studies, a vascularized interposition graft was recommended as the primary treatment when avascular necrosis was present; [26]

In another study, no association was found between the union rate following surgery and either the age of the patient or the interval between the original injury and subsequent nonunion surgery.[27]

Most of the published studies on vascularized bone grafting for all scaphoid nonunions have reported union rates of 80% to 100%, but only some of the nonunions had AVN.28,

Nonvascularized bone grafting is sufficient for most waist nonunions without AVN; however, vascularized bone grafting should be considered at least in cases of a long duration of nonunion, AVN of the proximal pole or failed previous surgery.29.

Recently, a meta-analysis found that vascularized bone grafting achieved an 88% union rate

compared 47% union rate with screw and intercalated wedge fixation in scaphoid nonunions with AVN.³⁰

Perlik and Guildford reported that increased density on the preoperative radiographs has only 40% accuracy for detecting proximal fragment avascularity, and thus many cases that were classified as AVN may actually have had satisfactory vascularity of the proximal pole.³¹

Boyer et al, reported 6 of 10 proximal pole nonunions healed with the 1,2 ICSRA bone graft. Straw et al also reported more discouraging results in that only 2 of 16 nonunions with AVN united with the 1,2 ICSRA bone graft.³³

Chang et reported a large series of 1,2 ICSRA bone grafts that were performed for scaphoid nonunions and showed that 71% of 48 nonunions healed and the union rate was 91% in the absence of AVN and 63% in the presence of AVN.³⁴

Treatment strategies for scaphoid nonunions remain still controversial. A long duration of nonunion, AVN of the proximal pole, and failed previous surgery are major factor effecting treatment of scaphoid non union .³⁵

CONCLUSION

We conclude tht vascularized bone graft with k-wires fixation is easy ,safe and effective in tratin scaphoid non union

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